

Traditional Conflict Resolution Techniques and Employee Engagement in Selected Manufacturing Companies in Southwest Nigeria

ADEJUWON, Joshua Adewale¹, AINA, Ebunoluwa Ibu-Anu², ABIODUN-AFOLABI Fadekemi Omogbonjubolanle³, ESO Ayoola Abimbola⁴

^{1,2}Department of Management and Accounting, Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria.

³Osgoode Professional Development, Osgoode Law School, York University, Toronto, ON Canada.

⁴Department of Finance, Lagos State University of Science and Technology, Lagos, Nigeria.

KEYWORDS: Traditional conflict resolution, Employee engagement, Manufacturing companies, Southwest

ABSTRACT

The study focused on the impact of traditional conflict resolution techniques on employee engagement in selected manufacturing companies in southwest Nigeria. The research adopted the survey research design. The population from this study consist of 3,137 employees from three manufacturing companies in Lagos, Nigeria, which include Coleman wire & cables with 121 employees, May & Baker Nig. Plc with 331 employees and Nigerian Breweries Plc with 2,685 employees. The sampling technique used in this research is the Convenience Sampling Technique. The sample size of 355 was determined using the Taro Yamane's Formula. Data was collected and were coded and managed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics such as simple percentages, frequencies were adopted used for demographic variables while hypotheses was tested multiple regression analysis. Findings showed that traditional conflict resolution techniques have a positive and significant effect on employee engagement. Based on the above findings, this study concludes that as conflict is inevitable and part of social life, the traditional conflict resolution technique is better utilised to resolve conflicts among employees and employers in workplace. The study therefore recommended that the government, should formulate laws, by-laws, regulations that can be implemented to increase honesty as the best policy in workers and employee engagement in the business world and the society.

Corresponding Author:
AINA, Ebunoluwa Ibu-Anu

Publication Date: 18 Nov.-2024

DOI: [10.55677/GJEFR/03-2024-Vol01E6](https://doi.org/10.55677/GJEFR/03-2024-Vol01E6)

License:

This is an open access article under the CC BY 4.0 license:
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

INTRODUCTION

Conflict among workers in any organisation is inevitable, if it is well managed, will be a catalyst for change and can have a positive impact on employee engagement in the organization, on the other hand, unmanaged conflict has a detrimental influence on both employee contentment and work engagement. When leaders dismiss workplace disagreement, they transmit the message that employee disengagement and undesirable behaviour are acceptable (Mwogereze, 2023). Conflict that is properly handled fosters open communication, collaborative decision-making, frequent feedback, and quick resolution (Hlongwane, 2017). Open communication and cooperation improve the flow of new ideas and deepen professional relationships, both of which may boost employee morale, regular feedback and quick conflict resolution can improve employee happiness and work engagement¹⁶. Meanwhile, a hostile work atmosphere that discourages dispute resolution can lead to poor employee engagement. Unmanaged conflict fosters dysfunctional communication and bad employee behaviour. Poor behaviour on the part of one employee has the potential to negatively impact overall staff morale, resulting in poorer employee engagement. Conflict can affect employee in both positive and negative ways, on one hand, conflict can challenge employees to think critically, share diverse perspectives, and improve their skills while on the other hand, conflict can also cause stress, frustration, and resentment which can lower employees' morale, satisfaction, motivation, zeal and loyalty. In an organisation, conflict may arise from conflict between employers and

employees over how revenue should be divided, how work should be done, how long and hard people should work, these reactions can be counterproductive to the company if the conflict is not well managed which will affect the employee engagement and productivity in disseminating the correct information to the company's stakeholders (Sasikala, Santhiya & Swatha, 2021).

As conflict is an inevitable phenomenon within a person, between two persons or among a group of people, with the advent of the British colonials into Nigeria, the traditional conflict resolution technique was in force, through customary mediation, diplomacy, compensation, restitution, diplomacy and cross-examination. Conflicts were diplomatically resolved without an ensuing enmity between the parties. The administration of the British establishing a master/servant relationship between the colonials and the locals was one of kindness, to the extent that locals were adopted as kinsmen by the colonial, this fact can be deduced from foreign names adopted and accepted by the locals. Matters of conflicts are resolved amicably by creating a free and fair hearing and listening field for the parties, the doctrine of equity was prevalent, hence, the resolution was either of a win/win or lose/lose situation, these cannot be said for the mode of modern-day conflict resolution techniques through court litigation which is termed as rigid where one party lose and the other wins.

Modern day conflict resolution technique is bedevilled with greed, self-centredness, and corruption to the extent that parties will rather go to court, rather than approve an amicable settlement on the matter of conflict. Employees would rather opt for court litigation than approach the management or human resources manager on the issue of contention, likewise the management would not want to give the employee an avenue to a fair hearing before taking any decision to either terminate the employees' appointment or other disciplinary method. There are some organisations where top management personnel feel intimidated when they see employees engaging in things like friendly disagreement or light political banter, hence, they make policies that discourages and kill employees' zeal to be involved in the organisation's success. For employees to be loyally engaged in their jobs, they must have that sense of belonging and contribution to the success of the organisation, creating an environment of open communication so that employees feel comfortable and confident to approach the management with their concerns without fear of repercussions. This will create a platform where organisational justice will be a practice of an organisation's system culture. Creating and implementing the policy of organisational justice is a positive influence to enhance employee engagement, workers are positively encouraged and the organisation benefits when justice is administered in a fair way (Faeq & Ismael, 2022). As organisations are made up of different people with different attitudes, beliefs, abilities and personalities, conflict becomes inevitable. No organisation can function effectively daily without encountering some form of conflict. As a result, conflict is the most prevalent, broad, and widespread phenomenon associated with group activity and interaction.

Thus, the research sought to examine the re- adoption of the traditional conflict resolution techniques as a way of settling misunderstandings between two or more parties on a particular matter of contention through dialog of customary mediation, compensation & sanction, restitution, diplomacy and cross examination with the organisational justice policy (Evwiehurhoma & Onouha, 2020). The specific problem is that some organisation leaders not leaving out manufacturing companies' leaders, lack the strategies to improve employee engagement. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to explore analyse the impact of traditional conflict resolution techniques on employee engagement in selected manufacturing companies in southwest Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Engagement

Employee Engagement (EE) can be defined as the means of harnessing the members of an organisation to excel in their work roles, to feel fully engaged, to have the opportunity to express their knowledge, skills and abilities and using their initiatives to get the work done in a more effective way (Albrecht, Furlong & Leiter, 2023). Employee engagement is a work role motivation, where the creation of a positive work environment induces the employees to work towards achieving the organisational objectives (Osam, 2022). In an environment with positive emotions, employees tend to excel in their assignments which in turn enhance the productivity of the organisation. Employee engagement results in giving positive outcome in the areas of increased level of motivation, sense of accomplishment, higher productivity and low employee turnover (Nugroho, 2022). Having a long-lasting, emotionally positive and a motivating working atmosphere is an impacting factor for a high level of employee engagement. If the aforementioned factors are taken into consideration it would result in work nature and outcome that assures a feeling of accomplishment, pleasant and productive work environment (Sundari & Narayanamma, 2020).

There is a link between organisational performance and engagement levels, with a well implemented HR policies, an organisation can retain a talented pool of employees with the necessary skills to work efficiently towards achieving the goals of the organisation (Johnson & Taylor, 2022). Job involvement is found to be associated with the engagement mentality of the employees. Hence in order to bring involvement, organisations should focus on its employee by taking care of their well beings and financial obligations, and to involve the employee in the sharing of authority and power as well, which means that incentives as an impact in the decision-making process of the organisations (Jayasena, Jusoh & Khatibi, 2023). Highly engaged employees are more productive, good advocates and positively influence organisational performance and corporate reputation and profitability (Osam & Dillard, 2021). Whereas, disengaged employees are not committed to the business vision and goals that leads to poor organisational outcomes,

therefore, in a constantly changing external environment, leaders must engage and empower the workforce in a way that improves job performance and business growth (Kirti & Goyal, 2022).

Dimensions of Employee Engagement

Cognitive Engagement: This means that employees are aware of and engaged with the organisation's overall plans and know what they need to achieve the best possible return on their job efforts (Budriene & Diskiene, 2020). Employee must understand their employer's vision and strategies to be fully engaged at this stage. They should also know what they must achieve to contribute as much as possible to the organisation. People who are passionate about their jobs and have more experience are more creative and make more confident decisions. From past study, it is observed that cognitive diversity can boost team creativity by up to 20% while lowering risk taking by up to 30%, and teams with more cognitive diversity tackle problems faster.

Physical Engagement: Employees who are physically engaged devote their emotional and physical energy to their work. People with a lot of energy have better overall health, which allows them to contribute more to the business (Budriene & Diskiene, 2020). To get the most of its workforce, a business needs to ensure that its employees are physically and mentally healthy, this has become even more important with the on-going public health crisis. As many companies offer medical health coverage for their employees, they also offer mental health services to those who need support. Hence, a healthy, active workforce is one that is also productive and creative.

Emotional Engagement: Employees' emotional commitment refers to their sense of belonging and confidence in the organisation and its members, emotional engagement is based on the process of managing one's emotions while at work (Budriene & Diskiene, 2020). People who are emotionally involved in their jobs are more likely to feel good and happy about it and experiencing such a positive effect gives them a sense of accomplishment and satisfaction for a job well done.

Traditional Conflict Resolution Techniques

Traditional conflict resolution refers to the customary practices and ways of resolving conflict within a particular community, (in this case the workplace), culture or the society, which as a result is often passed down through generations of organisation survival. The traditional conflict resolution techniques rely on established social structures, norms and values. One of the most fundamental problems that currently destabilize the survival of many organisations is the issue of workplace conflicts that arise between management and employees. It has been argued that most employees in an organisation are very often agitated and conflicted in their approach to issues which affect them as a group (Wonan, Oluo, Ake, & Benjamin, 2020). Most managers of the organisation perceive the workers as lazy, uncooperative individuals, who always hold secret labour meetings and plan drastic actions against the organisation; they constitute a threat to the labour interest, while workers in turn perceive the management as exploiting them. It is this perception arising from the management and the workers that sometimes result in conflict (Umana, 2019). The predictability of conflict (disputes) in the workplace has made it rational to put in place means of resolving conflicts whenever it occurs. Conflict resolution methods are greatly effective tools in managing conflict at work and thereby improvement in the environment of the workplace is achieved. There are various ways of adapting to traditional techniques in resolving conflicts. However, for the purpose of this research, the mode of traditional conflict resolution will be based on the following techniques, which are customary mediation by a respected leader or HR representative, Sanction & Compensation, Restitution, Cross-examination and Diplomacy. These techniques will be introduced for better understanding of the relevance to motivate employee engagement.

Customary Mediation

Mediation is a facilitative popular form of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR), in which the mediator assists the parties in resolving conflict by facilitating communication between them and by fostering a friendly and productive environment in which the discussion may occur, because the legal system is rigid, mediation can make parties create ideas that may not be practical in court. This is a mode of conflict resolution, where a friendly decision arises with the help of a third party referred to as the mediator without recourse to the court of law. The mediator, who is only a facilitator, does not interfere in the decision taken at the resolution, it is a voluntary and flexible process where the parties to the conflict are under no obligation to agree to the settlement. Mediation is highly beneficial in resolving conflict as it cost effective and efficient, the process is confidential and flexible, and it preserves relationship and encourages open communication which makes it faster and convenient than litigation. However, the agreement arrived at through mediation shall be binding upon the parties, only if the parties agree to it, this is a process where the parties are in total control over the final decision (Ele & Auquasama, 2020). Mediation processes have more than one type of approach, depending on the type and style of conflict that are available in resolving conflict. These different types of mediation are not mutually exclusive, that is, a mediator can solely make use of one style or conducting the process by using two or more styles of mediation.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

This theory is anchored on Kahn's Theory of Employee Engagement. Employee engagement theory is the formal idea that by challenging, supporting, and inspiring employees, organisations increase the satisfaction and maximise the output of the employees. This theory posits that companies with high levels of worker motivation and loyalty enjoy employee engagement benefits such as

lower turnover and less absenteeism, higher customer satisfaction, bigger bottom lines (profit, people, and place) and increased creativity and innovation. William Kahn, a psychologist, defined the term employee engagement as the harnessing of organisation employees to their work roles; in engagement, people employ and express themselves physically, cognitively, and emotionally during performance of their roles (Cetin, 2019). His work focuses on the conditions that allow employees be more committed to their workplace, three factors that affect an employee connection with the organisation mission, company culture, and daily tasks of their roles are identified to be; meaningfulness, safety and availability. Meaningfulness refers to the purpose behind the work. An employee with foresights to understand the company's vision and mission is possible to make a significant impact. Also, an employee that feels psychologically safe in the work environment, possessing the confidence to face criticism or consequences from co-employees or higher management, is more likely to contribute positively to the organisation. Lastly, availability is when an employee possesses the capability to perform both physical and mental roles. Even though every human being has limits, challenges are better for growth and satisfaction, that is, an employee should be made to feel that the demands of the position occupied are reasonable and achievable (Cetin, 2019). Kahn's theory upheld a profound understanding of employees' needs and a more holistic approach to employee engagement. Engagement occurs when employees are seen and treated like a real person, then they can harness their full potential to their work. A good working environment encourages employee engagement by serving to be a safe space where every employee can voice their opinions without fear of reprimand from the managers. The theory is not without its criticism, as the theory was initially developed in the western context, hence its applicability may not be assimilated due to diverse cultural settings and that the theory subjectively focused on individual engagement thereby neglecting the importance of groupings in teams and organisational engagement (Cetin, 2019).

Empirical Review

Adewale (2022) explored the importance, effect of employee engagement in the manufacturing sector, was examined from a mid-size company's point of view, where there are manufacturing sheet metal press components. The study was carried out in a company located near Chennai on a convenience sample of 118 respondents through the distribution of structured questionnaires to employees of the company. The study found the satisfactory level of the employees regarding various factors related to their commitment towards their company. Conclusively, there is a positive attitude found among employees and they are actively engaged towards their company.

Moruku and Oluwafemi (2023) investigated conflict management and employees' engagement in the insurance sector in Nigeria. The objective was to establish the effect of conflict management style on employees' engagement in insurance company in Lagos state using a survey research design. Leadway insurance company was surveyed by random sampling technique. A total population of 310 regular employees were investigated with a sample size of 228. The validity of the instrument was determined using content and construct validity while Cronbach Alpha was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. Bivariate linear regression analysis was used to analyse the hypothesis with the aid of statistical package for social science (v26.0). From the study it was found that avoidance conflict management had significant effect on emotional employee engagement in Leadway Assurance Lagos state, Nigeria ($\beta = 0.351$, $t = 3.973$, $p < 0.05$). It concluded that conflict management promotes employees' engagement in the insurance sector in Nigeria. Centred on the findings, the study recommended amongst others that insurance companies should sensitize and train their employees about the conflict management and what it concerns.

Osabiya (2015) conceptualizes employee engagement as one of the important drivers for a successful organisation. The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate the factors affecting employee engagement at macro level, i.e, organisational-related factors, personal-related factors, team-related factors and job-related factors. By reviewing various literature studies, the researcher found that these are all factors influencing the employees for higher level of engagement in organisations. Thus, leads to better employee performance and productivity and reducing the turnover intention. This paper suggests that organisations must frequently check the employee performance management so as that they would be able to find in which factor influences the employees for low engagement. By doing so, the organisations can thrive in their performance and productivity.

Diaka, Yande, Ahmed and Kpelai (2022) attempts to find out ways to identify best practices in conflict management in the workplace and ways to improve organisation and work life through better employment relations. The study focus was on factors that informed organisation's decision to find an alternative means of handling conflict through traditional discipline and grievance procedures, the barriers and facilitators to integrating mediation into workplace practice and culture. The hypotheses formulated were to determine the source of conflict and conflict resolution in the Nigeria Public Service sector. Descriptive statistics was used to analyse the data collected from a sample of 170 employees. The findings arrived at from the experimental survey of conflict management resolution in public sector indicated that conflict can be resolved through compromise between employees and the management. In conclusion, the recommendation was that workers should be allowed to get more involved in decision making process in Nigeria Public Service for the reason of mitigating the rate of conflict and this can be accomplished with effective communication network between the employees and the management.

Adeolu-Akande, Sanya, and Oyedokun (2020) evaluated the impact of conflict management on organizational performance in public sector institutions. The relevant empirical and theoretical literatures were evaluated, and the study is based on conflict theory. A descriptive survey research design of the ex post facto kind was used. The Taro Yamane model yielded a sample size of 342. It was

chosen via stratified random sampling from 2345 employees of the six purposefully selected ministries in the Oyo state civil service, which served as the study population. Data was gathered via questionnaires. Only 318 surveys were deemed viable, resulting in a 93.00% response rate. To investigate the association between conflict management and organizational performance, a descriptive and regression analysis was conducted using SPSS. The results showed that there is a strong association between conflict management and organizational performance ($r = 0.672$; $p < 0.05$). Findings further revealed that causative factors of conflict do not have a significant relationship with organisational performance (p -value $(0.51 > 0.05)$). However, there is a significant relationship between conflict management styles and organisational performance (p -value $= 0.000 < 0.05$). This study concludes that effective conflict management contributes to enhanced employees' productivity and would eventually improve organisational performance. The study recommended that management should effectively manage conflicts before they escalate to an unmanageable level, by using appropriate strategies.

Mishra, Sharma and Anand (2022) studied the effect of employee engagement dimensions (vigor, dedication and absorption) on the performance of Mikap Nigeria Limited, Makurdi was examined. The cross-sectional survey design and questionnaires were utilised to collect data from employees of the company. Adopting a census sampling approach was used for the study on employee population of 112. The study used multiple regression analysis for data presentation and the formulated hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS version 23). Findings revealed that vigor engagement has significant effect on organisational performance ($\beta = .173$, $p = .000$), dedication engagement has significant effect on organisational performance ($\beta = .302$, $p = .000$), and absorption engagement has significant effect on organisational performance ($\beta = .237$, $p = .012$). The study recommended amongst others that managers of organisations should improve vigor among employees since it improves staff performance and enhance organisational performance.

Ele, Ekpenyong, Okongo and Eneh (2024) evaluated the effects of conflict management strategies on employee performance in the University of Teaching Hospital. Survey research design employed a structured questionnaire in the collection of data for analysis on a population of 550 with sample size of 226 using Krejcie and Morgan table of 1970. The hypothesis was tested and analysed using a simple linear regression analysis model applying SPSS version 23. The findings from the study were that there are positive effects of conflict avoidance strategy on employees' performance of the University Teaching Hospital, there is also a significant effect of conflict collaboration strategy on employees' commitment to goals achievement. Based on the findings, the study recommended that organisation's management should monitor and mediate on issues that can lead to conflicts for the enhancement of employees' performance by adopting avoidance strategies. In conclusion of the study, management should give attention to conflict situations as urgently as possible in order to avoid those factors that can hinder employees' motivation and commitment to goal achievement. Mediators are encouraged to be engaged on a constant basis.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopts the survey research design. The research was carried out on Three (3) manufacturing companies. The total population from this study consist of 3,137 employees from three manufacturing companies located in Lagos, Nigeria, which the results are from Coleman wire & cables of 121 employees, May & Baker Nig. Plc of 331 employees and Nigerian Breweries Plc of 2,685. These manufacturing companies were purposively selected from three sectors of the manufacturing industry in Nigeria. The sampling technique used in this research is the Convenience Sampling Technique. The researcher made use of the 3,137 population from the 3 companies and sample size is determined using the Taro Yamane's Formula

$$n = \frac{N}{(1 + Ne^2)}$$

where:

n = signifies Sample Size

N = signifies total population under study

e = signifies the Margin error (0.05)

e = 0.05

$e^2 = 0.0025$

N = 3,137

For this research of a population of 3137, 0.05 level of significance is used

$1 + Ne^2 = 8.84$

$$n = \frac{N}{(1 + Ne^2)} = \frac{3,137}{1 + 3,137(0.0025)} = 355$$

Survey questionnaire was administered on 355 respondents across the 3 manufacturing companies. However, 30% of the sample size is added for non-response and wrongly filled questionnaire.

That is, $355 + 107 = 462$ (to include 30% of calculated sample size for non-response and wrongly filled questionnaire). 462 questionnaires were distributed to 462 staffers. 405 questionnaires were retrieved this number represented 87.6% response rate. Data analysis was done after the data gathered are coded and managed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and was

analysed using descriptive and Inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics such as simple percentages, frequencies were adopted used for demographic variables while hypotheses was tested multiple regression analysis.

RESULTS AND PRESENTATION OF DATA

Table 1: Demographic Characteristic of Respondents

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	20-30 years	116	28.6%
	31-40 years	231	57%
	Above 40 years	58	14.3%
Gender	Female	175	43.2%
	Male	230	56.8%

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey 2024

A total number of 116 (28.6%) respondents were within the age range of 20 – 30 years. 231 (57%) respondents were within the age range of 31 –40 years, 58 (14.3%) respondents were within the age range of 40 years and above. This report show that majority of the respondents were within the age range of 31 –40 years, it is therefore, inferred that employees in the selected manufacturing companies comprise of active and energetic people in their prime age. It shows distinction between male and female. 175 (43.2%) of the respondents are female while 230 (56.8%) % are male respondents. Thus, majority of the respondents were males.

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question: What will be the effect of traditional conflict techniques on employee engagement in the selected manufacturing companies in southwest Nigeria?

Table 2: Descriptive Analysis for the Response on Traditional Conflict Resolution Techniques

Traditional Conflict Resolution Techniques	SA	A	UD	D	SD	Std.Dev	Mean
The company’s value is to quickly resolve conflicts before it escalates		282 69.6%	0	0	0	.460	1.70
The employees have direct access to the management to report grievances	290 71.6%	115 28.4%	0	0	0	.451	1.28
The company makes room for employees’ fair hearing through cross- examination of witnesses	58 14.3%	58 14.3%	0	289 71.4%	0	1.05	3.43
It is for good the company to resolve the conflict between itself and its employees by resorting to the Court.	173 42.7%	232 57.3%	0	0	0	.495	1.57
It is good when a company’s conflicts are amicably resolved between the parties	348 85.9%	57 14.1%	0	0	0	.348	1.14
The Human Resource Manager should mediate conflicts between the employees and employers.	232 57.3%	173 42.7%	0	0	0	.495	1.43
The traditional conflict resolution techniques of customary mediation, compensation & sanction, diplomacy etc. are effective conflict resolution tools.	174 43%	173 42.7%	58 14.3%	0	0	.701	1.71
The employer is empathetic towards the employees’ views.	174 43%	173 42.7%	58 14.3%	0	0	.701	1.71
The employers should resolve and handle conflict in a face-to-face meeting with the parties involved in the conflict.	116 28.6%	231 57%	58 14.3%	0	0	.640	1.86
The employers in resolving the conflict should be objective and neutral.	347 85.7%	58 14.3%	0	0	0	.701	1.29

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey 2024

According to results in Table 2 30.4% of respondents strongly agree that the company’s value is to quickly resolve conflicts before it escalates, 69.6% agree on average, the respondents indicated that it is best to resolve conflicts before it escalates has a mean of 1.70. Results also indicated that 71.6% of respondents strongly agree that employees must have direct access to the management to report grievances, 28.4% agree on average the number of respondents who are of the opinion that employees must have direct access to the management to report grievances is 1.28. Results also indicated that 14.3% strongly agree and agree respectively that company makes room for employees’ fair hearing through cross- examination of witnesses while 71.4% disagree. On average, the response for fair hearing through cross examination was 3.43. It is also reported that 42.7% strongly agree and 57.3% agree that it

is good for the company to resolve the conflict between itself and its employees by resorting to the Court, on average, the response was 1.57. According to results in Table 2 85.9% of respondents strongly agree and 14.1% agree that it is good when a company’s conflict is amicably resolved between the parties. On average, the respondents indicated that it is good when a company’s conflict are amicably resolved between them has a mean of 1.14. Results also indicated that 57.3% of respondents strongly agree that Human Resource Manager should mediate conflicts between the employees and employers. On average, the respondents indicated mediation in conflict between employee and employers has a mean of 1.43. Results also indicated that 43% of the respondents strongly agree that “traditional conflict resolution techniques of customary mediation are effective, 42.7% agree, and 14.3% undecided. On average, the respondents indicated that it is an effective conflict resolution tools with a mean of 1.71. When respondents were asked whether their employer is empathetic towards the employees’ views, 43% strongly agree, 42.7% agree while 14.3% remained undecided, on average the response had a mean of 1.71. Results also showed that 28.6% and 57% strongly agree and agree respectively that employers should resolve and handle conflict in a face-to-face meeting with the parties involved in the conflict while 14.3% remained undecided. On average, the response had a mean of 1.86. Results on neutrality and objectivity of employers showed that 85.7% and 14.3% strongly agree and agree respectively and the mean for the response was 1.29.

Presentation of Data

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between traditional conflict resolution techniques and employee engagement in selected manufacturing firms in southwest Nigeria.

In order to test the hypothesis, linear multiple regression analysis was used. In the analysis, the values of Employee Engagement were regressed on the values of traditional conflict resolution techniques. The data for traditional conflict resolution techniques was generated by summing responses of all items used to measure the variable while that of Employee Engagement was generated by adding responses of all items used to measure the variable. The regression test results are presented in Tables 3.

Table 3: Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis for the Effect of Traditional Conflict Resolution Techniques and Employee Engagement in Selected Manufacturing Firms in Southwest Nigeria.

Model	Beta	T	Sig.	R	R ²	Adj. R ²	Anova Sig.	F(df)
(Constant)	-.224	-4.915	.000					
TCR	1.323	50.923	.000	.930 ^a	.865	.865	0.000	2593.201

Dependent Variable: employee engagement

Predictors: (Constant), TCR

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey 2024

Table 3 presents the results of multiple regression analysis for the effect of traditional conflict resolution techniques and employee engagement in selected manufacturing firms in southwest Nigeria. Table 3 presents a model summary which establishes how the model equation fits into the data. The Adj R² was used to establish the predictive power of the study’s model. From the results, traditional conflict resolution techniques have strong positive and statistically significant relationship with employee engagement in selected manufacturing firms in southwest Nigeria. (R = .865, p=0.000).

The Adjusted coefficient of determination (Adj R²) of 0.865 shows that traditional conflict resolution techniques explained 86.5% of the variation in employee engagement in selected manufacturing firms in southwest Nigeria while the remaining 13.5% variation in employee engagement is explained by other exogenous variable different from traditional conflict resolution techniques considered in this study. This result suggests that traditional conflict resolution techniques influence 86.5% of employee engagement in selected manufacturing firms in southwest Nigeria.

Table 3 presents the results of ANOVA (overall model significance) of regression test which revealed that traditional conflict resolution techniques have a significant effect on employee engagement in selected manufacturing firms in southwest Nigeria. This can be explained by the F-value (2593.201) and low p-value (0.000) which is statistically significant at 95% confidence interval. Hence, the result posited that traditional conflict resolution techniques adopted by the manufacturing firms in southwest Nigeria influenced employee engagement.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Generally, this research contributes to the understanding and ratifying the traditional conflict resolution techniques on employee engagement in selected manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

The results from the study indicate that majority of the respondents agreed that traditional conflict resolution techniques have a positive and significant effect on employee engagement. These findings corroborate the result of another study which found that traditional conflict resolution techniques have direct control on employee engagement and there is a direct relationship between

other exogenous variations of conflict resolution. It also flows with the submissions of other empirical studies which have identified a positive impact of traditional conflict resolution techniques on employee engagement.

Also, these results have been supported by findings of various empirical studies which has highlighted that traditional conflict resolution technique is one of the strongest attitude factors influencing employees in organisations¹. In other words, TCR technique highly affects employee engagement assignment in organisations. Other studies mention that TCR technique has a mediating effect on employee in organisational environments. However, not much is known about the mechanism through which TCR techniques affects employee in general. The findings of this result were also supported by the finding of another study whose results showed that TCR technique fully mediated the effects of organisational justice to employee engagement.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study examined the impact of traditional conflict resolution techniques on employee engagement in selected manufacturing companies in southwest Nigeria. The study concluded that traditional conflict resolution technique has strong positive and statistically significant relationship with employee engagement in selected manufacturing companies in southwest Nigeria. It concluded that, as conflict is inevitable and part of social life, the traditional conflict resolution technique is better utilised to resolve conflicts among employees and employers in workplace. These resolution techniques will foster harmony between parties in conflict, as it is, conflict when constructively managed will boost employee morale to be engaged in the discharge to their duties to the organisation, rather than proceeding to the court of litigation for which the resultant outcome will create disharmony amongst groups.

This study offers the following recommendation:

1. The concept of traditional conflict resolution technique will create a positive impact on employees and will make for positive employee engagement. Therefore, the government, should formulate laws, by-laws, regulations that can be implemented to increase honesty as the best policy in workers and employee engagement in the business world and also the society.
2. Employees should be given active voice in contributing to the success of the organisation from their array of experiences in handling tasks. Knowing that they have a listening ear through fair hearing in conflict resolution will make employees more loyal and engaged in the discharge of tasks. Having an interaction with the management will bring out the most positive attitude in employees.

REFERENCES

1. Adeolu-Akande, M. A., Sanya, E. A. O. & Oyedokun, G. E. (2021). Conflict management and organisational performance of selected public sector establishments in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. *Fountain University Osogbo Journal of Management (FUOJM)*, 5(3), 75-90.
2. Adewale, H. O. (2022). Effect of conflict management on employee engagement in the insurance sector: Evidence from Leadway Assurance, Nigeria. *The Strategic Journal of Business and Change Management*, 9(3), 274-287.
3. Albrecht, S. L., Furlong, S. & Leiter, M. P. (2013). The psychological conditions for employee engagement in organisational change: Test of a change engagement model. *Organisational Psychology*, 14.
4. Budriene, D. & Diskiene, D. (2020). Employee engagement: Types, levels and relationship with practice of HRM. *Malaysian eCommerce Journal (MeCJ)*, 4(2), 42-47.
5. Cetin, O. I. (2019). *Conflict and Conflict Management in Organisations*. In Book: *Management and Information Systems*. Bahattin Karademiv (Ed). Academician Publishing House Inc., 9-28.
6. Diaka, H., Yande, H. M., Ahmed, I. A. & Kpelai, T. (2022). Employee engagement performance of Mikap Nigeria Limited, Makurdi. *Benue Journal of Management and Contemporary Studies*, 2(1), 63-101.
7. Ele, A. A. & Auquasama, A. V. (2020). Alternative dispute resolution dimensions on employees' performance in Nigeria work organisations: A theoretical perspective. *American International Journal of Business and Management Studies*, 2(2), 28-40.
8. Ele, A., Ekpenyong, B. O., Okongo, N. J. & Eneh, S. I. (2024). Effects of conflict management strategies on employers' performance in the University of Calabar Teaching Hospital, Calabar, Nigeria. *African Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research*, 7(2), 121-136.
9. Evwiehurhoma, D. E. & Onouha, B.C. (2020). Knowledge management tools applications and organisational performance of manufacturing firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Knowledge and Dynamic Systems*, 13(2), 2020, 1-16.
10. Faeq, D. K. & Ismael, Z. N. (2022). Analysing the relationships between organisational justice and job performance. *International Journal of Engineering, Business and Management*, 6(5), 14-25.
11. Hlongwane, P. Employee grievance mediation process: Rethinking its modalities. *International Journal of Applied Business and Economic Research*, 15(20), 537-549.

12. Jayasena, W. L. V., Jusoh, M. & Khatibi, A. (2023). The impact of psychological conditions on employee engagement of administrative staff in national universities, Western Province in Sri Lanka. *Journal of Law and Sustainable Development*, 11(10).
13. Johnson, K. A. & Taylor, M. (2020). *Engagement as Strategy: A Framework for Strategic Communication*. Research Handbook on Strategic Communication, 384-399.
14. Kirti, K. & Goyal, S. (2022). Adoption of Employee Engagement Practices at the Workplace: Higher Educational Institutes. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(2), 2022, pp.507-517.
15. Mishra, A., Sharma, V. & Anand, G. (2022). Improving and enhancing the level of employee engagement in modern era. *Paripex-India Journal of Research*, 11(5), 51-53.
16. Moruku, R. K. & Oluwafemi, P. O. (2023). Employee engagement strategies and organisational conflict management. A study of hospitality industry in Delta State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Innovation Research*, 11(50), 27-41.
17. Mwogereze, R. (2023). Workplace conflicts and employee performance in institutions in Kamuli district. *International Journal of Conflict Management*, 4(1), 78-88.
18. Nugroho, S. H. (2022). The role of human resources management in organisational perspective. *Global Journal of Engineering and Technology Advances*. 10(3), 12-18.
19. Osabiya, B. J. (2015). Conflict management and resolution in Nigeria public sector. *Review of Public Administration & Management*, 4(8), 107-120.
20. Osam, E. K. & Dillard, N. (2021). Deconstructing the meaning of engagement: An intersectional qualitative study. *Human Resource Development International Journal*, 24(5), 511-532.
21. Osam, E. K. (2022). Book review: Employee engagement: A research overview. *New Horizon in Adult Education and Human Resource Development*, 34(1), 63-65.
22. Sasikala, P., Santhiya, C. & Swatha, K. (2021). Conflict management in workplace. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt*, 18(8), 4749-4758.
23. Sundari, N. & Narayanamma, P. L. (2020). A study on employee engagement: The key to improving performance. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*, 7(1).
24. Umana, E. A. (2019). Conflict resolution strategies and organisational performance: an exploratory analysis. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 7(5).
25. Wonan, L., Oluo, H. I., Ake, O. & Benjamin, E. (2020). Conflict management strategies and organisational performance of Rivers State Civil Service. *International Journal of Contemporary Academic Research*, 1(2).